

A QUALITATIVE STUDY OF LEADERSHIP IN EXCELLENT SCHOOL: A CORRESPONDENCE ARTICLE

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ABSTRACT

This review explores leadership in excellent schools. Leadership is recognized as a crucial factor in achieving school success and high performance. This review paper aims to investigate leadership characteristics, strategies, and practices employed in schools that have achieved excellence. The literature review indicates that future schools must be supported with adequate infrastructures and the implementation of education based on the achievement of quality, equity, effectiveness-efficiency, and relevance. The studies have indicated the significant factors essential in achieving high school performance. By understanding these practices, educational institutions can learn from their success and implement effective leadership approaches to enhance their school performance.

Keywords: *leadership, excellent school, school principal*

INTRODUCTION

Leadership is a critical factor in the success of any school, and it is especially important in excellent schools that strive to provide high-quality education to their students. To achieve their goals, these schools need leaders who possess a range of qualities and skills, including the ability to inspire and motivate others, foster a positive learning culture, and develop and implement a clear vision for the school's future. According to a study, effective school leaders share several key characteristics, including the ability to shape a vision of academic success for all students, to create a climate hospitable to education, to cultivate leadership in others, to improve instruction, and to manage people, data, and processes to foster school improvement (Adams, 2018). Other studies have identified additional qualities of great school leaders, such as visionary leadership, community building, and emotional intelligence (Aguilar, 2014).

Empowering teachers to take on leadership roles within the school community is a powerful strategy. Bryk and Schneider (2002) argued that distributed leadership contributes to a culture of collective responsibility and efficacy. Educational leaders can identify and nurture the strength of individual teachers, providing opportunities for them to lead initiatives, mentor colleagues, or contribute to decision-making processes. Such empowerment not only builds confidence but also enriches the overall professional competence of the teaching staff. These will help the teachers to be at their maximum potential and optimum.

By implementing these strategies, leaders contribute not only to the confidence of their teachers but also to the overall competence and success of the entire educational community.

Research Questions

The study research questions attempt to address the strategies of school leaders in becoming a successful school or institution. The goal of this review is to identify the leadership strategies, and how to bring the environment in a comparable excellent school.

Research question 1: How does the principal's leadership style contribute to the development of an excellent school in terms of school vision?

Research question 2: To what extent does the principal's leadership impact the overall culture and environment of the school, influencing the school's ability to lead students towards achieving excellent competencies?

METHODOLOGY

This correspondence article limits and concentrates on leadership in excellent schools. To gain more information about the article, browsing and searching using different search platforms concerned about leadership and review articles were identified. The article met the related criteria, such as a qualitative study about leadership and governance, at least in Asian settings relevant to our culture, language used in writing is English and not translated. The selected topic should not be subjective, within the area of interest, must be open for public access, and not restricted. References of additional information from other relevant research articles were taken to make it comprehensive.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the author, the school community that includes in the interview were principal, teachers, and non-teaching personnels since everyone contribute the development of this study.

Research question 1: How does the principal's leadership style contribute to the development of an excellent school in terms of school vision?

According to the author, the school must have clear and organized school's vision formed to produce graduates to be excellent in science, technology, arts, skilled and independent. The process of formulating the school vision are as follows: 1) formulation by a team; (2) deliberations of all school members regarding the results of the vision formulation by the team; (3) endorsement of the school's vision by stakeholders; and (4) socializing the school's vision to school members and the community (Bafadal, et.al, 2020). The principal's way of making all school members feel that they have the vision of the school is to integrate the vision of the school into learning activities and school activities whether it is extra-curricular or co-curricular activities.

Research question 2: To what extent does the principal's leadership impact the overall culture and environment of the school, influencing the school's ability to lead students towards achieving excellent competencies?

The quality of learning culture developed by schools is learning based on good program planning, controlled implementation, and evaluation that meets more than 8 minimum education standards. The formulation of the quality of learning culture is the preparation of school programs by a team of 8 standards, implementation of programs in each standard, and evaluation of program implementation (Bafadal, et.al.2020). However, the learning environment in the form of school facilities and infrastructure that supports the quality of learning culture is outdoor or indoor learning, laboratories, libraries, school health units, gazebos, fish ponds, mosques, halls, and so on (Bafadal, et.al. 2020). To make this vision materialize, the school financial support team will go to extend the funds needed for the planning, but due to time constraint and budget rules, the process of it for some times (Bafadal, et.al 2020).

By implementing these practices, schools can enhance students' achievement, improve teacher effectiveness, and create a positive and inclusive learning environment. It is essential for aspiring and current school leaders to develop these leadership skills to contribute to the success of their schools.

Conclusions

The findings also point to leadership's dynamic and adaptive nature in excellent schools. Leaders are willing to embrace change, adopt innovative practices, and continuously reflect on their performance. This adaptability allows schools to navigate challenges, respond to evolving educational landscapes, and maintain a focus on student learning outcomes.

This study presented that excellent schools can be identified based on the school performance, teacher performance, and the number of students who successfully finished their respective school program (Junior or Senior High School program).

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author declares that strict adherence to the ethics of research was maintained, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided and there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings.

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REFERENCES

- Bafadal, Ibrahim, et.al. (2020). *Leadership in excellent education*. A qualitative study. Atlantis press. Retrieved from <https://www.atlantis-press.com/proceedings/icite-20/125948651>
- Adams, J. (2018). *Five qualities of strong school leaders*. 2018. Retrieved from 5 Qualities of Strong School Leaders – UWSuper
- Aguilar, Elena (2014). *What makes a great school leader?* Edutopia. Retrieved from What Makes a Great School Leader? | Edutopia
- Bryk, A. S., & Schneider, B. (2002). *Trust in schools: A core resource for improvement*. Russell Sage Foundation.